

NPR 7150.2 and NASA's SWE Handbook

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What Is Software Engineering?

Software Engineering is not programming!

“a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation and maintenance of software; that is, the application of engineering to software” IEEE

The term was coined by Margaret Hamilton in 1963-1964, director of the Software Engineering Division of the MIT Instrumentation Laboratory, which developed on-board flight software for NASA's Apollo program.

“It was a memorable day when one of the most respected hardware gurus explained to everyone in a meeting that he agreed with me that the process of building software should also be considered an engineering discipline, just like with hardware.” Margaret Hamilton

NASA's Software Definition (From IEEE)

NPR 7150.2

Software is defined as:

- (1) computer programs, procedures and possibly associated documentation and data pertaining to the operation of a computer system
- (2) all or a part of the programs, procedures, rules, and associated documentation of an information processing system
- (3) program or set of programs used to run a computer
- (4) all or part of the programs which process or support the processing of digital information
- (5) part of a product that is the computer program or the set of computer programs

This definition applies to:

- Software developed by NASA,
- Software developed for NASA,
- Software maintained by or for NASA,
- Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) software,
- Government off-the-shelf (GOTS) software,
- Modified off-the-shelf (MOTS) software,
- Reused software,
- Auto-generated code,

- Embedded software,
- The software executed on processors embedded in programmable logic devices (see NASA-HDBK-4008, Programmable Logic Devices (PLD) Handbook),
- Legacy software,

Software Is Not All the Same

flight software \neq *Non-flight software*

engineering software \neq *general purpose software*

safety critical software \neq *non-safety critical software*

... and it shouldn't be treated the same!

NPD 1000.0 Strategic Management & Governance Handbook
NPD 1000.3 The NASA Organization
NPD 1000.5 Policy for NASA Acquisition

Governing Documents

Current NASA Software Documentation Tree

(with a few related non-software documents in gray)

Policy

Procedural Requirements

Standards

Handbooks & Guidebooks

Center Level Directives

Purpose of the NASA Software Engineering Requirements, NPR 7150.2

- Software engineering is a **core capability** for NASA's missions and supporting infrastructure.
- **Support the implementation of NASA's policies**
- **Provide a minimal set of requirements**
- **Support NASA programs and projects in accomplishing their planned goals**

NPR 7150.2 History

Nov 2004 – Original
 Nov 2009 – Rev A
 Nov 2014 – Rev B
 Aug 2019 – Rev C
 Mar 2022 – Rev D

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About NASA's Software Engineering Requirements (NPR 7150.2)

- The NASA Office of the Chief Engineer is responsible for the NPR
- The NPR shall be applied to all software development, maintenance, operations, management, acquisition, and assurance activities
- Includes engineering and assurance requirements
- Requirements are levied on Center organizations as well as projects
 - Applicability of requirements is determined through the use of a NASA-wide definition of software classes
- To find the document online go to NASA Online Directives Information System (NODIS)
 - http://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/main_lib.html
 - Look for NPR 7150.2

NASA NATIONAL AERONAUTICS AND SPACE ADMINISTRATION

+ NASA Portal
+ NODIS Library
+ NASA Internal Access

NODIS Library

NASA ONLINE DIRECTIVES INFORMATION SYSTEM

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Directive ID	Subject	Expiration Date
NPD 7010.1L	Processing Legislative Proposals	January 29, 2023
NPD 7100.10F	Curation of Institutional Scientific Collections (Revalidated w/Change 1)	May 26, 2026
NPR 7100.1B	Protection of Human Research Subjects	February 15, 2024
NPD 7100.8F	Protection of Human Research Subjects	April 29, 2024
NPR 7120.10A	Technical Standards for NASA Programs and Projects	July 21, 2022
NPR 7120.11A	NASA Health and Medical Technical Authority (HMTA) Implementation	September 8, 2025
NPD 7120.4E	NASA Engineering and Program/Project Management Policy	June 26, 2022
NPR 7120.5F	NASA Space Flight Program and Project Management Requirements	August 3, 2026
NPD 7120.6A	Knowledge Policy for Programs and Projects	December 16, 2024
NPR 7120.7A	NASA Information Technology Program and Project Management Requirements	August 17, 2025
NPR 7120.8A	NASA Research and Technology Program and Project Management Requirements (Updated w/Change 2)	September 14, 2023
NPR 7123.1C	NASA Systems Engineering Processes and Requirements (w/Change 2)	February 14, 2025
NPR 7150.2C	NASA Software Engineering Requirements	August 2, 2024
NPD 7170.1	Use of Human Research Genetic Testing	February 22, 2023
NPD 7330.1I	Approval Authorities for Facility Projects (Revalidated w/Change 1 on September 23, 2021)	January 6, 2026
NPD 7410.1H	Management of Contract and Grant Support Services Obtained from External Sources (Revalidated 8/14/2018)	August 27, 2023
NPD 7500.1D	Program and Project Life-Cycle Logistics Support Policy	June 2, 2022
NPR 7500.2	NASA Technology Transfer Requirements	July 19, 2022
NPD 7620.1I	Official Names for Major NASA Projects (Revalidated w/Change 2)	February 14, 2025
NPR 7900.3D	Aircraft Operations Management	May 1, 2023
NPD 7900.4D	NASA Aircraft Operations Management, Updated with Change 1, March 10, 2015	December 7, 2022

Visual Overview of NPR 7150.2

30 “Institutional” Requirements (Chapter 2)

NPR 7150.2

Applicable to All Classifications

OCE	SMA	Center Director/Delegate(s)		
Lead Software Engineering Initiative	Lead Software Assurance and Safety Initiative	Staff and advance software engineering capability	Measure for Improvement	Maintains contributor list
Benchmark Center’s Capabilities against this NPR	Benchmark Center’s SWA and SW Safety Capabilities	Establish and execute software processes	Establish and maintain software cost repo	Ensure Proper transfer of software
Benchmark Center Mapping Matrices	Review Center’s Mapping Matrices	Comply with NPR per Classification in Appendix C	Contribute to Agency PAL (Process Asset Library)	Contract Officer: Ensure NPR is on contract
Authorize Compliance Appraisals	Authorize Appraisals against requirements	Report project status	Define content of SW documentation	Tech Authority: Assess against NPR
Provide Software Engineering Training	Provide Software Assurance Training	Maintain list of projects	Ensure Government rights to Software	OCE, SMA, OCIO: agree on tailoring
Maintain Process Asset Library (PAL)	Makes Decisions on Tailoring IVV Rqmt	Establish and maintain software Metrics	Ensure reuse software conforms to policies	Project Manager: Update plans per Classification

100 NPR Requirements* - *Applicable Based on Classification*

NPR 7150.2

Software Management (Chapter 3)

Lifecycle (Chapter 4)

Lifecycle Support-Ch5

Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MC/DC	Verify Cyber Protection	Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Cyclomatic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Rqmts	Identify CM Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs. Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop, Test Data Upload Procedures	Establish CM Procedures	Analyze Software Measurements
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier Inputs	Record Adversarial Actions	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Reuse/COTS Equally	Maintain CM Records	House Measurement Data
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec Plan (IPEP) if IVV	Perform and Certify as CMMI	Perform Bi-Directional Traceability	Implement, Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops, Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CM Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define Milestones	Store Cost in Repo	Provide IVV Artifacts	Identify Reuse Rqmts	Establish Rqmts	Adhere to Coding Standards	Use Accredited Tools	Deliver Products	Develop Release Procedures	Measure Software Volatility
Developer Report Status	Develop Schedule	Respond to IVV Findings	Evaluate Reusability	Map to System Rqmts	Perform Static Code Analysis	Update Plans	Complete Verification	Participate in Audits	Track Defects
Dev'er Provide Product & Metrics	Regularly Review with Stakeholders	Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety Rqmts	Unit Test	Validate in High-fidelity	Maintain	Determine, Manage Risk	Determine Severity Levels
Developer to Provide Access to Source Code	Dev'ers Report Schedule	Adhere to 8739.8 SWA & SW Safety Std	Identify Cyber Risks	Track Rqmt Changes	Repeat Unit Test	Track Code Coverage Metrics	Archive	Peer Review Rqmts, Plans, Code, Test	Assess reuse, COTS defects
Comply with this NPR	Train	Do Safety-Crit items: SWE-134	Implement Cyber Protection	Track Corrective Actions	Develop VDD	Validate Metrics in Test	Plan CM	Follow Basic Peer Review Process	Assess Process Defects

*Note SWE-220 Cyclomatic Complexity has 2 shalls, counted as 1 here

Class A&B (All 100)

C (92)

D (64)

E (12)

Requirements

NPR 7150.2

Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MC/DC	Verify Cyber Protection	Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Cyclomatic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Reports	Identify CMI Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs. Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop, Test Data Upload Procedures	Establish CMI Procedures	Analyze Software Measurements
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier Inputs	Record Adversarial Actions	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Reuse/COTS Equally	Maintain CMI Records	House Measurement Data
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec Plan (IPEP) if IVV	Perform and Certify as CMMI	Perform Bi-Directional Traceability	Implement Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CMI Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define Milestones	Store Cost in Repo	Provide IVV Artifacts	Identify Reuse Reports	Establish Rqmts	Adhere to Coding Standards	Use Accredited Tools	Deliver Product	Develop Release Procedures	Measure Software Volatility
Developer Report Status	Develop Schedule	Respond to Dev Findings	Evaluate Reusability	Map to System Rqmts	Perform Static Code Analysis	Update Plans	Complete Verification	Participate in Audits	Track Defects
Developer Provide Product & Metrics	Regularly Review with Stakeholders	Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety Reports	Unit Test	Validate in High-fidelity	Maintain	Determine Manage Risk	Determine Severity Levels
Developer to Provide Access to Source Code	Developers Report Schedule	Adhere to 8739 & SWA & SW Safety Std	Identify Cyber Risks	Track Rqmt Changes	Repeat Unit Test	Track Code Coverage Metrics	Archive	Peer Review Rqmts, Plans, Code, Test	Assess reuse, COTS defects
Comply with this NPR	Train	Do Safety-Critical Items: SWE-134	Implement Cyber Protection	Track Corrective Actions	Develop VMS	Validate Metrics in Test	Plan CMI	Follow Basic Peer Review Process	Assess Process Defects

Class F Requirement Applicability (OCIO Authority)

NPR 7150.2

Make/Buy	Tailor	Classify	Perform MC/DC	Verify Cyber Protection	Validate	Accredit Tools	Regression Test	Track Changes	Record Peer Review Results
Plan	Mapping to this NPR	Maintain Classification Records	Track Cyclomatic Complexity	Use Secure Coding	Architect	Plan, Report Tests	Test Safety Points	Identify CM Items	Measure Software
Track Actual vs. Expected Plan	Establish and Acquire OTS	Plan SA & IVV	Plan Auto-Gen lifecycle	Use Cyber Static Analysis	Review Architecture	Test	Develop, Test Data Upload Procedures	Establish CM Procedures	Analyze Software Measurements
Determine Acceptance Criteria	Establish Cost	Ensure IVV	Receive Auto-Gen Supplier Inputs	Record Adversarial Actions	Design	Manage Configuration	Test Reuse/COTS Equally	Maintain CM Records	House Measurement Data
Determine Deliverables	Include Specific Cost Items	Ensure IVV Project Exec Plan (IPEP) if IVV	Perform and Certify as CMMI	Perform Bi-Directional Traceability	Implement, Code	Evaluate Test Results	Plan Ops, Maintenance, Retirement	Perform CM Audits	Compare Measured vs. Expected
Define Milestones	Store Cost in Repo	Provide IVV Artifacts	Identify Reuse Rqmts	Establish Rqmts	Adhere to Coding Standards	Use Accredited Tools	Deliver Products	Develop Release Procedures	Measure Software Volatility
Developer Report Status	Develop Schedule	Respond to IVV Findings	Evaluate Reusability	Map to System Rqmts	Perform Static Code Analysis	Update Plans	Complete Verification	Participate in Audits	Track Defects
Dev'er Provide Product & Metrics	Regularly Review with Stakeholders	Determine Safety Criticality	Assess Cyber	Include Safety Points	Unit Test	Validate in High-fidelity	Maintain	Determine, Manage Risk	Determine Severity Levels
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Comply with this NPR	Train	Do Safety-Crit items SWE-134	Implement Cyber Protection	Track Corrective Actions	Develop VDD	Validate Metrics in Test	Plan CM	Follow Basic Peer Review Process	Assess Process Defects

Software Engineering Handbook

NPR 7150.2

The screenshot displays the NASA Software Engineering Handbook website. The top navigation bar includes 'Book A. Introduction', 'Book B. 7150 Requirements Guidance', 'Book C. Topics', 'Book D. Label Search', and 'Book E. Tools, References, & Terms'. The main content area is titled 'Content based on NPR 7150.2C' and 'Content based on NPR 7150.2D'. The left sidebar shows a table of contents with chapters 1 through 5. The main content area is divided into three columns: 'Chapter 3. Software Management Requirements', 'Chapter 4. Software Engineering Life Cycle Requirements', and 'Chapter 5. Supporting Software Life Cycle Requirements'. Each column lists specific requirements and their descriptions.

Chapter 3. Software Management Requirements	Chapter 4. Software Engineering Life Cycle Requirements	Chapter 5. Supporting Software Life Cycle Requirements
3.1 Software Life Cycle Planning SWE-033 - Acquisition vs. Development Assessment SWE-013 - Software Plans SWE-024 - Plan Tracking SWE-034 - Acceptance Criteria SWE-036 - Software Process Determination SWE-037 - Software Milestones SWE-039 - Software Supplier Insight SWE-040 - Access to Software Products SWE-042 - Source Code Electronic Access SWE-139 - Shall Statements	4.1 Software Requirements SWE-050 - Software Requirements SWE-051 - Software Requirements Analysis SWE-184 - Software-related Constraints and Assumptions SWE-053 - Manage Requirements Changes SWE-054 - Corrective Action for Inconsistencies SWE-055 - Requirements Validation 4.2 Software Architecture SWE-057 - Software Architecture	5.1 Software Configuration Management (SCM) SWE-079 - Develop CM Plan SWE-080 - Track and Evaluate Changes SWE-081 - Identify Software CM Items SWE-082 - Authorizing Changes SWE-083 - Status Accounting SWE-084 - Configuration Audits SWE-085 - Release Management SWE-045 - Project Participation in Audits 5.2 Software Risk Management

NPR 7150.2A

NPR 7150.2B

NPR 7150.2C

NPR 7150.2D

- Guidance material to help the NASA workforce implement the software engineering requirements in NPR 7150.2 and promote best practices across the Agency in software engineering.
- Addresses topics of interest identified by the Software Engineering community of practice
- Provides guidance for all of the software engineering requirements contained in NASA's NPR 7150.2, plus topics
- Guidance material includes requirement specific guidance, rationale, examples, best practices, lessons learned, references, tools and templates

<https://sweb.nasa.gov/>

Handbook Version Transition Page

The screenshot shows the NASA Software Engineering Handbook website. At the top, there is a banner with the text "NASA Software Engineering Handbook Content based on NPR 7150.2D" and "NASA ENGINEERING NETWORK". Below the banner is a navigation menu with tabs for "A. Introduction", "B. Institutional Requirements", "C. Project Software Requirements", "D. Topics", "E. Tools, References, and Terms", and "F. SPAN (NASA Only)". A search bar is located to the right of the navigation menu. The main content area is titled "Book A. Introduction" and contains the following text:

Created by Bruce J Guy, last modified by Haigh, Fred Douglas. (HQ-KA000)[PEROT] on Apr 15, 2022

1. Welcome | 2. SWEHB Introduction | 3. Title Material | 4. Resources | 5. Accessing Other Versions of SWEHB

The version of the handbook that you are viewing is noted in the header image. Clicking on this image, while on any page of the SWEHBVD, will take you back to the Introduction page for this version.

To access other versions of the Software Engineering Handbook use the links below:

- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2A](#)
- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2B](#)
- [Click here to go back to the Software Engineering Handbook from NPR 7150.2C](#)
- You are already in the Software Engineering and Software Assurance Handbook from NPR 7150.2D

Four versions of the NASA Software Engineering and Assurance Handbook, NASA-HDBK-2203 are available for use (see Tab 5 to access the versions of the handbook)

- The original version of the handbook - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2A. NPR 7150.2A had an effective date of November 19, 2009, to the expiration date of November 19, 2014.
- Revision A - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2B. NPR 7150.2B had an effective date of November 19, 2014, to the expiration date of August 2, 2019.
- Revision B - addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2C and the requirements in the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety standard, NASA-STD-8739.8A. NPR 7150.2C had an effective date of August 2, 2019, to the expiration date of August 2, 2024. NASA-STD-8739.8A 278 has an effective date of June 10, 2020.
- Revision C - Addresses the NASA Software Engineering Requirements in NPR 7150.2D, and the requirements in the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety standard, NASA-STD-8739.8A. NPR 7150.2D had an effective date of 03/08/2022, to the expiration date of 03/08/2027. NASA-STD-8739.8A 278 has an effective date of June 10, 2020.

NPR 7150.2D is the latest version of the NASA Software Engineering Requirements.

NASA-STD-8739.8A is the latest version of the NASA Software Assurance and Software Safety Standard

5.1 SWE History

The SWE History Summary includes all SWE numbers and their history of use in all versions of the Software Engineering Handbook.

Click [SWE History](#) to view.

Remember...

- **NPRs and Standards (including NPR 7150.2) are not intended to be “one size fits all documents”**
 - **They have built-in tailoring**
 - **Software Classification (Class A, B, C, D, E, or F)**
 - **Tailoring of the Software Classification requirements**
 - **There is a level of compliance and rigor specified that is associated with the class of the software to be built or acquired**
 - ***Part of your job as is to carefully consider what tailoring is necessary and build time into your schedule to complete it***
- **There are tailoring procedures via Center and HQ Engineering Technical Authority (ETA)**

Use good software engineering and software assurance judgement on which requirements should be implemented by your project

Questions

Additional information can be found at

<https://nen.nasa.gov/web/software>

<https://swehb.nasa.gov/>

<https://sma.nasa.gov/sma-disciplines/software-assurance>

<https://nsc.nasa.gov/SMAToolbox/>

<https://software.nasa.gov>

<https://open.nasa.gov>

<https://developer.nasa.gov>

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